

UTILIZING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AT EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation. A student is under pressure to study and comprehend the material especially a foreign language quickly due to the speedy development of modern civilization. Today, mastering at least one foreign language is becoming a crucial component of a specialist's professional competence. Therefore, it is important to focus on the effectiveness and caliber of the foreign language learning process. Interactive methods are the most successful for learning languages. The article's main goal is to outline the function of interactive teaching strategies for English. The following objectives were set forth in order to accomplish the stated goal: to outline the primary interactive techniques and provide some usage examples. This article discusses using interactive teaching techniques to teach English. Many interactive teaching techniques are discussed in this article, with a focus on the value of the TPR method in the teaching of English.

Keywords: teaching, approach, interaction, create, interactive, role-playing games, children, process, TPR.

Introduction. As is customary, the teacher explains, speaks, and demonstrates while the learner listens, writes, and memorizes. To find out what the child has learnt, surveys, assessments, and quizzes are administered. Although not the only passive teaching strategy, this one is one of them. There is also an active strategy. The interaction between the student and the teacher constitutes it. In our work, we employ interactive techniques. They emphasize greater student connection with each other as well as with the teacher, as well as the importance of student involvement in the learning process. Children collaborate in pairs and small groups to complete projects, test hypotheses, and take on the role of teachers during interactive classes. It is not required for the teacher to explain a new subject when we start studying it. We can start from the opposite: we give an example, and the learners offer theories on which rule is applied in this situation. It turns out that learners "invent" rules on their own and pick them up as they play. We collaborate with teachers to design every lesson, hold weekly planning sessions, and consider how to structure lessons to be engaging. Numerous interactive techniques are available, including role-playing games, projects,

brainstorming, and lectures. For instance, we want learners to pick up language rapidly¹.

Teachers only offer dictations in lyceums. We took a different approach and wrote 10 new terms before coming up with a role-playing game. Children rode on rollers to the signpost where they read and remembered a new word before going back and writing it down from memory. Excellent instruction that is short, effective, and engaging for learners. They role-play real-life situations during interactive sessions, hold conversations, and watch movies and the news in an effort to make the learning process as realistic as possible. We strictly adhere to the norm that the entire lesson be taught in English. After the first lesson, a youngster will occasionally claim to their mother, "Mom, everything was in English, I didn't understand anything, I won't go anymore." Parents begin to fear. Here, it matters how the teacher teaches. Our goal when speaking in English is to make ourselves understandable to non-native speakers. It's challenging; I have to use gestures to explain. For instance, I might command the boys to "Open your books" while gesturing to the appropriate action².

By repeating it, they automatically learn the sentence. As it turns out, despite my training, they are incapable of comprehending this. The learners become accustomed to your explanations in Uzbek and wait for you to translate before offering assistance. Children are compelled to comprehend when the entire lesson is taught in English. We constrain them, so if you come, you must listen and make an effort to comprehend. Another method that is frequently utilized in the classroom is total bodily response, which is on the way. In lessons that employ the TPR approach, students actively participate in the learning process by moving around, dancing, and repeating words and phrases with various emotional undertones. The total physical response (TPR) method, also known as the whole physical response method, is a popular way to teach young children in prelyceum and primary lyceum foreign languages. As a result, the technique works with all types of perception, including kinesthetic, visual, and auditory learners. By moving his body in a certain way, the teacher communicates a term or concept to his students while having them pronounce the word or phrase along with him. For instance, the guys follow the teacher's instructions in English during the first stage³.

As a result, the teacher introduces new terminology through activity. The students call the action once the teacher models it in the second step. Although the majority of parents support gaming lessons, some still prefer more conventional

¹ Kevin Yee. Language Teaching Methods, 2000.

² Richards, Jack C.; Theodore S. Rodgers. Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. Cambridge UK, 2001.

³ Van Hattum, Ton. The Communicative Approaches Rethought, 2006.

methods. We persuade them by pointing out that it's crucial to teach the child to communicate as well as to read, write, and translate. mainly because learning a language is necessary for communication. The TPR method involves mimicking teacher cues or gestures to help students remember new words or phrases. Children imagine eating with a spoon when the term spoon is used, and they grin when the word smile is used⁴. For instance: The "Confusion" activity. While touching the other, the facilitator calls attention to one portion of the body. Says Nose, for instance, while indicating the ear. The players' task is to directly touch the body part that he calls. It turns out that by using interactive, or as specialists refer to them, communicative, approaches, we can accomplish two goals at once: we can encourage the child's interest in the topic while simultaneously learning the language. What more can be said about how pleased the boys are to be given the option of playing video games for homework?

It turns out that you can increase your knowledge with their assistance. People who are "interactive" collaborate and have an impact on one another. This scenario suggests a chat or a discourse. As a result, both interactions between students and the teacher as well as interactions between students exclusively are the focus of these strategies. Students must participate actively in the learning process. The goal of interactive learning is to establish unique circumstances that encourage all students to participate in the learning process, allowing them to comprehend and realize everything that occurs, influence one another, and contribute on their own while developing friendly and supportive relationships. Role plays, brainstorming, case studies, presentations, and conversations are the most widely used techniques. They improve their ability to communicate, think logically, and engage in various sorts of intellectual activity, including analysis, synthesis, comparison, and generalization. These student-centered teaching tactics are ideal for getting students more actively involved in learning new concepts, abilities, and approaches⁵.

Role plays, as is well known, promote interdisciplinary interactions, relate theory to the actual demands of the professional world, and foster the abilities that future specialists will need. They also make university learning more effective and educational. The crucial component is role acting, which offers the chance to develop abilities that are challenging to learn under typical learning circumstances. Scripted and unscripted role plays are the two possible outcomes. A text book example might be

⁴ Westwood P. What teachers need to know about teaching methods. Camberwell: ACER Press, 2008. – 105 p.

⁵ Каминская Е.В. Разнообразие современных интерактивных методов обучения иностранному языку в ВУЗе / Е.В. Каминская // Язык и мир изучаемого языка. Вып. 7. Саратов: Саратовский социально экономический институт (филиал) РЭУ им. Г.В. Плеханова, 2016. – С. 159 – 165.

used by the teacher during a scripted role play. The notion of having everyone break out into pairs and speak to their partner while playing different parts is a fantastic one for a warm-up exercise. Non-scripted role plays are those in which students are assigned to characters and are required to speak with partners using whatever knowledge they may have. A general English class might use a few of these. This can be modified to fit a circumstance. Students who complete case studies gain the following advantages:

- 1) They can learn by doing. Case studies give students the chance to assume the roles of decision-makers in actual businesses and resolve the problems they encounter without putting themselves or the firm at danger;
- 2) enhances students' capacity to pose pertinent questions in a particular problem-solving scenario;
- 3) exposes students to a broad range of businesses, organizations, roles, and degrees of responsibility. Students gain the adaptability and self-assurance they need to handle a range of duties and responsibilities in their employment as a result. Additionally, it enables students to choose careers with greater knowledge;
- 4) it improves students' understanding of management theory by giving practical examples of the underlying ideas. They give conceptual debates life by supplying rich, fascinating knowledge on actual business scenarios;
- 5) this information reflects the reality of managerial decision-making in the real world. In this situation, pupils must decide based on incomplete information. Cases show the ambiguity and complexity that often accompany management issues;
- 6) aids in understanding and addressing the various points of view and views of the other team members. Unquestionably, this helps students develop their interpersonal and communication abilities;
- 7) it gives them a holistic perspective on management. The integration of theories and concepts learned in many functional areas, like as marketing and finance, is a key component of managerial decision-making. Students are exposed to this management reality through the case technique⁶.

Conclusion. We may therefore draw the conclusion that interactive teaching techniques help to maximize the learning process when studying English after describing the various ways. They want to make teaching English language communication more effective by putting in place mechanisms for motivation. The benefits of using interactive methods in the learning process for students include the closest possible simulation of real-world professional conditions, a high degree of

⁶ Куимова М.В. The use of case study method in teaching English as a foreign language in technical university / М.В. Куимова. // Молодой ученый. 2010. – № 1-2 (13). – Т. 2. – С. 82 – 86.

student autonomy, decision-making in situations involving creative competition, the development of skills for spontaneous speech, encouraging the development of organizational skills in students, and removing the barrier between language study and its practical application.

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